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ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS ITS EFFECTS AND APPLICABLE METHODS

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HOW PSYCHOLOGY DEAL WITH ENVIRONMENT?

"Environmental Psychology is field of study that examines the inter relationship between environment and human affect cognition and behaviour" (Bechtel & chorchman 2002, Gilford 2007)

Environment Types

Natural / Water / Air / Land / Mountain / Forest / Vegetation

Mane Built - Home / Road / School / College / Market / Industries of etc.

General orientation to nature and environment (according Florence Cluson (1953)

- People as subjugated to nature
- People as above nature
- People as part of nature

How Environment affects human body (Change in the environment due to human activities)

Environmental problems and its effects

Environmental problems	Types	Physical	Social	Mental
Natural Disaster	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Flood ▪ Tsunami ▪ Draught ▪ Snow fall ▪ Earthquake 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Stunned ▪ Numb ▪ Fearlessness ▪ Irrational 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Separation ▪ Homeless ▪ Scarcity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Anxiety ▪ Stress ▪ Frustration ▪ Depression ▪ Phobia ▪ Loneliness
Noise Unpleasant sound (above 90 db)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Intensity of noise ▪ Pitch ▪ Reflection ▪ Periodicity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ High level of catecholamine ▪ High blood pressure ▪ Digestive disturbance ▪ Allergy ▪ Cardiovascular disease ▪ Hearing loss ▪ Headache 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Negative Attraction ▪ Aggression ▪ Violent Physical / Mental ▪ Lack of helping behaviour 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of perceptual control ▪ Learned helplessness ▪ Memory loss ▪ High arousal level ▪ Distraction of attention ▪ Lack of performance ▪ Changing mood ▪ Instability ▪ Anxiety / stress
Temperature and heat (above 32 ⁰ C)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Dust storm ▪ Cyclone ▪ Tornado 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Effect on thermo regulatory mechanism ▪ High BP/High heartbeat, heart attack ▪ High skin conductance ▪ sweating ros used ▪ Pelpitation ▪ Fatigue 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of coping behaviour (Escape) ▪ Aggressive behaviour ▪ Disturbed interpersonal relationship 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Irritability ▪ Anxiety ▪ Low stress tolerance ▪ Unhappiness
Air Pollution	<p>External</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ozone ▪ Sulphur oxide ▪ Nitrogen oxide ▪ Carbon mono oxide <p>Internal</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of Oxygen (Hypoxia) ▪ Dumb and Deaf, Blindness ▪ Epilepsy ▪ Headache ▪ Fatigue 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Low work performance ▪ High reaction time ▪ Driving problem ▪ High rate of accident 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Emotional disturbance (Due to nitrogen di oxide) ▪ Lack of adjustment (Due to sulphur di oxide) ▪ Memory Loss

Environmental problems	Types	Physical	Social	Mental
	(Industrial/homes) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sulphur di oxide ▪ Nitrogen di oxide ▪ Cadmium ▪ Mercury 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Cancer ▪ Immunity ▪ Air Pollution syndrome (APS) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of interpersonal attraction (due to ammonia sulphur di oxide) ▪ Increase aggressive behaviour (Due to ethyl mrcaptain) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mental Retardation (MR)
Water pollution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Industrial waste ▪ Sewage waste ▪ excessive use of plastic or fertilizers ▪ Carelessness of people towards water pollution etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Health hazards ▪ Reduction in solar energy and decreased rate of photosynthesis ▪ Oxygen deficiency in water ▪ Decrease in fresh water 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Violent behaviour ▪ Low quality of life 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Tension ▪ Anxiety ▪ Unhappiness ▪ Depression

Applicable methods for the solution of environmental problems

ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION

- Respect for Mother Nature (water / air / land / forest / animals / vegetation).
- Include environment topics in syllabus at school / college / university level.

- Govt. org / NGOs / semi govt. org / should have awareness programme for environment (organize workshop and seminar).
- Organisation / institution should mark important environment days.

ENVIRONMENTAL PROMPT - Improvement for good behaviour

- Appreciation for appropriate behaviour.
- Punishment and fines for inappropriate behaviour.
- Monetary help /donations.
- Plantations.
- Self-role model.
- Give written information.
- Simple and effective quotations and instruction.

REINFORCEMENT METHOD

- Monetary awards by Govt. (+ve behaviour occur).
- Relaxation in tax benefits (+ve behaviour).
- Makes laws / acts / rules.
- Penalty by increasing tax (-ve).

FEEDBACK - Information about behaviour modification

- Set goals and target.
- Target achieved or not.
- Goal attained or not.
- Feedback result in positive behaviour.